

HUMAN-CENTRIC AI-ENABLED EXTENDED REALITY APPLICATIONS FOR THE
INDUSTRY 5.0 ERA

D5.3 – TRAINING PLATFORM FOR OPERATOR 5.0 v1

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Definition
3D	Three Dimensional
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AL	Active Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BCI	Brain-Computer Interface
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
COBOT	Collaborative Robots
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DoA	Description of the Action
DTLS	Datagram Transport Layer Security
AWS EC2	Elastic Compute Cloud
AWS S3	Simple Storage Service
GenAI	Generative Artificial Intelligence
GB	Gigabyte
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHz	Gigahertz
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDT	Human-centric Digital Twin
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
I5.0	Industry 5.0
IdP	Identity Provider
IoT	Internet of Things
MBit	Megabit
ms	Millisecond
MR	Mixed Reality
NSAI	Neurosymbolic Artificial Intelligence
OAuth	Open Authorization
OS	Operating System

PDF	Portable Document Format
RAM	Random-access Memory
RBAC	Role-based Access Control
SCORM	Sharable Content Object Reference Model
SCTP	Session Controller Transport Protocol
SLAM	Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping
SRTP	Secure Real-time Transport Protocol
SDK	Software Development Kit
SSO	Single Sign-On
TPAT	Training Programs Authoring Tool
UI	User Interface
vCPU	Virtualised Central Processing Unit
VE	Virtual Environments
VR	Virtual Reality
WAIV	Wing Anti-Ice Valve
WebRTC	Web Real-Time Communication
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality
XRRP	XR Repository Plugin
X RTP	XR Training Plugin

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D5.3, titled *Training Platform for Operator 5.0 v1*, is the first deliverable within WP5, *XR-Enabled Operator 5.0 Training*, which aims to design, build and provide an advanced cloud-based XR training platform to revolutionize industrial operator training through the incorporation of immersive XR technologies, advanced AI models and human-centric digital twins. The platform serves as a central hub for hosting, orchestrating, and delivering XR training applications while integrating cutting-edge AI, personalisation, and digital twin capabilities deployed for Industry 5.0 scenarios and tailored for Operator 5.0. The deliverable presents the initial progress in the design, technical integration, and implementation of the XR5.0 Training Platform. It defines the foundational building blocks and core components that underpin the platform's development throughout the project. Additionally, it introduces the initial pilot application scenarios and outlines the planned refinements aimed at achieving the objectives established in WP5.

This deliverable synthesises efforts across four tasks, Task T5.1-T5.4, that correspond to the platform's core functionality structure around key components: (i) transforming traditional training material into XR-compatible content, (ii) establishing a cloud-based XR asset repository for managing and integrating training assets and programs, (iii) orchestrating XR devices and assets for seamless deployment via XR streaming, and (iv) providing a dedicated tool for creating and customizing training programs within the platform. This modular approach enhances scalability, adaptability, security and ease of integration across various industrial sectors, boosting the human-centric concept of Industry 5.0.

The XR5.0 Training Platform will enable industrial enterprises and workers to visualise and navigate complex processes within immersive XR environments, guided by a virtual training instructor. Designed to support Industry 5.0 use cases, the platform will provide intelligent, human-centric training applications that enhance workforce skills and operational efficiency. By offering XR content tailored to common industrial scenarios, the Operator 5.0 training platform will empower workers to fully leverage XR technologies, improving their adaptability and expertise. Furthermore, the project will integrate AI-driven, person-centric XR solutions, ensuring personalised and effective training experiences that align with the evolving demands of Industry 5.0.

The XR5.0 Training Platform aligns with Industry 5.0 goals by prioritizing a human-centric and ethical design approach, integrating AI-driven adaptability and transparent decision-making within immersive learning environments. By enabling workers to interact dynamically with XR content tailored to real-world industrial applications, the platform fosters efficient, personalised training experiences. Furthermore, the platform's emphasis on adaptability, trust, and collaborative stakeholder feedback ensures that it remains resilient and sustainable, reinforcing the broader objectives of Industry 5.0.

Deliverable D5.3 serves as a baseline for the refinements and advancements to be detailed in Deliverable D5.4, *Training Platform for Operator 5.0 v2*, which represents the next iteration of D5.3.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Objectives of the Deliverable

The XR5.0 project, under Work Package 5 (WP5): "XR-Enabled Operator 5.0 Training" aims to design and build a cloud-based XR training platform to train industrial operators in an immersive environment wherein XR5.0-enabled XR applications will be hosted and streamed to XR end-devices. This first version of the deliverable D5.3 aims to outline the framework of the proposed XR5.0 Training Platform by describing the system architecture and the building blocks that make up the XR5.0 Training Platform, the technical interplay between the components, the core features and benefits enterprises achieve through the platform and the way in which XR5.0 pilots will implement in real-world applications and realise the benefits of the platform.

The architectural design, workflows, and technical considerations presented in this report are based on the Description of Action (DoA) and feedback from technical partners and end-user requirements within the XR5.0 project that are tailored towards Industry 5.0 applications and Operator 5.0 users. The deliverable, across its length, emphasises on the platform's scalability, security, and alignment with enterprise requirements. The objectives of this report are structured to provide a comprehensive understanding of the XR training platform's technical foundation, functionality, and real-world applications.

The key objectives of this report are:

- Defining the Technical Architecture – Providing a structured analysis of the core components and building blocks that constitute the XR5.0 Training Platform, along with their functional roles, technical requirements, and interdependencies.
- Explaining Component Integration – Describing how the platform's cloud infrastructure, orchestration mechanisms, and XR streaming capabilities interact to create a cohesive and scalable training ecosystem.
- Detailing Key Platform Features – Presenting an in-depth overview of the platform's unified interface, centralised user and application management, security framework, real-time analytics, and training tools that enable efficient deployment and use.
- Assessing Real-World Deployment – Demonstrating how the platform will be implemented in industrial training scenarios, showcasing its role in enhancing workforce skills, improving operational efficiency, and facilitating seamless learning experiences.
- Ensuring Industry 5.0 Alignment – Evaluating how the platform meets Industry 5.0 principles by fostering human-centric, sustainable, and AI-driven training solutions that enhance adaptability, trust, and collaboration between humans and technology.

By addressing these objectives, this deliverable provides a comprehensive and structured analysis of the XR5.0 Training Platform, ensuring clarity in its design, implementation, and scalability for future industrial applications.

1.2 Relation to other WPs and Deliverables

The XR5.0 Training Platform described in this deliverable serves as the foundational infrastructure that enables the deployment, orchestration, and management of XR-based training applications. However, its design, functionalities, and real-world validation are deeply interlinked with the other work packages (WPs) of the XR5.0 project (refer to Figure 1), mentioned below:

- WP2 - Specifications, Architecture and EU XR Platform Integration
- WP3 – Human Centric Digital Twins and XR Personalisation
- WP4 – AI/XR Symbiosis for Augmented Intelligence
- WP6 – XR5.0 Apps Integration, Validation and Evaluation

Figure 1 - WP5 as the central key work package interlinked with WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP6

WP2 defines and establishes the technical specifications for XR5.0, XR5.0 application requirements and reference architecture of the XR platform upon which the XR5.0 Training Platform is built. The XR5.0 Training Platform follows the specifications standards discussed within WP2 and described in D2.2 - “Reference Architecture Model and Technical Specifications v1” as well as builds on top of the reference architecture. Therefore, WP2 acts as a conceptual blueprint for the design and development of the XR5.0 Training Platform developed within WP5.

WP3 focuses on personalisation and human-centric digital twins (HDT) that enhance user-adapted training experiences. The XR5.0 applications that are hosted on the XR5.0 Training Platform integrate the services from the HDT to deliver personalised XR training experiences taking into consideration the worker characteristics, skills and roles. The XR5.0 Training Platform designed to provide user analytics could potentially provide insights into learning patterns, engagement levels and skill progression and find-tune training delivery. Similarly, WP4 focuses on developing novel AI models (AL, NSAI, GenAI) and integrating them with XR interfaces for visualizing AI explanations and recommendations. The XR5.0 applications, hosted on the platform, will include the interfaces with the application logic and user interface (UI) to communicate with the WP4-based AI models for specific training scenarios. Therefore, the XR5.0 Training Platform developed within WP5 serves as an enabler for WP3 (Human Digital Twins) and WP4 (AI/XR) inspired technical components for enhanced training experiences.

Finally, WP6 validates the XR5.0 Training Platform and its applications through real-world testing across 6 pilots with varied industrial training applications. WP5-driven Training Platform provides the environment where real-world XR training applications with training programs are hosted and deployed and the pilots within WP6 provide the necessary training material and resources for the pilot use cases (Refer to D6.1 - “Use Cases Co-Creation and Pilot Sites Preparation v1” that provides a comprehensive synthesis of the XR5.0 project’s efforts to integrate Extended Reality (XR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) into industrial settings with a human-centric approach). The user feedback collected from each pilot within WP6, including usability and training effectiveness, would be used to refine the platform’s architecture and features in WP5. WP6 ensures that concepts and components from WP2, WP3 and WP4 work seamlessly within the WP5-

driven platform and serve as the final validation stage ensuring the XR5.0 Training Platform meets the practical training requirements.

In summary, WP5 is a critical component of the overall XR5.0 project, acting as the execution layer that integrates the technical architecture and specifications (WP2), personalisation and Human Digital Twins (WP3), AI-enhanced capabilities (WP4) and real-world deployment and validation (WP6). WP5 will integrate technologies developed in WP3 and WP4, training materials from the UCs of WP6 as well as from external stakeholders to build a unified XR5.0 Training Platform for operators in I5.0. The relationships between these WPs form a cohesive ecosystem, ensuring that the XR5.0 Training Platform is technically robust, scalable, and impactful supporting diverse XR training applications.

1.3 Relation to other WP5 tasks

The XR5.0 Training Platform, developed within WP5 - XR-Enabled Operator 5.0 Training, combines the focal points of all tasks within WP5. Each task serves as a building block of the XR5.0 Training Platform and is crucial to the overall functionality of the platform as designed within the XR5.0 project (refer to Figure 2).

- T5.1 - XR Training Materials and Demonstrators
- T5.2 - Cloud Management of XR Training Assets
- T5.3 - XR Assets and Devices Orchestration
- T5.4 - Training Programs Development

Figure 2 - The interplay of the 4 key tasks in the development of the XR5.0 Training Platform

T5.1, led by partner IML, will develop and deliver XR-based training materials which are mapped into the XR environment from traditional training materials and are tailored for specific industrial scenarios and use cases. The XR5.0 Training Platform provides the necessary tools and infrastructure to enable the mapping of conventional training materials such as manuals and videos into interactable 3D models and spatial experiences ensuring the seamless adaptation of training materials to immersive environments. This process aims to enhance the operator’s skills and knowledge in operating and maintaining industrial

equipment and processes by leveraging spatial learning and real-world contextualisation within XR5.0 applications hosted on the platform.

T5.2, led by partner HOLO, will develop a cloud-based XR asset repository that will allow industrial enterprises to upload and store training materials and assets such as manuals, 3D models, videos and metadata. The XR asset repository will be integrated within the XR5.0 Training Platform to enable real-time streaming of XR training materials to industrial operators hence serving as a fundamental component of the XR5.0 Training Platform. T5.2 aligns with the overall cloud-based approach of the Training Platform ensuring scalability, security, orchestration control and adherence to ethical and privacy concerns, allowing multiple organizations to manage their respective training materials with appropriate access control mechanisms. This integration streamlines the deployment of XR training modules, enabling real-time updates and remote access to the latest training materials.

T5.3, led by partner HOLO, focuses on the orchestration of XR training assets and XR devices using Hololight Hub, the backbone streaming platform of the XR5.0 Training Platform, to enable seamless integration and coordination of XR assets and devices supporting XR-driven training of industrial operators. T5.3 will also leverage Hololight Stream to enable device-agnostic XR streaming of XR5.0 applications using cloud resources. The orchestration layer of the XR5.0 Training Platform facilitates real-time streaming, resource allocation, user and application management as well as synchronization of training programs, ensuring consistent user experience. Furthermore, the platform enables admins/managers to track progress and review user performance analytics.

An essential feature and service of the XR5.0 Training Platform is the XR Training Management System developed within T5.4 (led by partner IML) with a focus on training programs development. The task will focus on developing and managing immersive training programs offered by the XR5.0 Training Platform that enables trainers and instructional designers to develop structured training programs by linking materials from the cloud repository (T5.2). The training programs developed will address the needs of operators, in terms of skill, roles and expertise taking into consideration the different industrial environments. The task will focus on providing a unified interface, via the XR5.0 Training Platform, that will allow users/operators to access training programs assigned to them by their admins/managers who in turn upload materials (T5.1) and create training programs. The training programs created are stored in the cloud repository (T5.2), making them readily available for deployment across different XR devices. The platform also supports user analytics, allowing trainers to monitor trainee performance and refine training content based on real-time data insights.

The XR5.0 Training Platform serves as the foundation for executing the four key tasks within WP5 necessary for immersive training implementation. By mapping traditional materials to XR, providing a scalable XR assets cloud repository, managing XR assets, users, XR5.0 apps, and device orchestration, and offering a dedicated training program tool, the XR5.0 Training Platform offers an integrated and efficient approach to XR-based training enhancing accessibility, engagement, and effectiveness in industrial and educational training applications.

1.4 Structure of the Deliverable

This report is organised to provide a clear understanding of the platform's architecture, features, use cases, and future work. The deliverable begins with Section 1 - Introduction, outlining the objectives and scope of the XR5.0 Training Platform. It establishes the platform's alignment with Industry 5.0 principles and provides a roadmap for the document.

Section 2 – Background and Motivation presents a review of existing XR training solutions, identifying industry trends, limitations, and the gaps that the proposed platform aims to address. This section contextualises the need for a scalable, secure, and AI-enhanced XR training solution.

Section 3 – System Architecture details the technical foundation of the platform, describing its core components, cloud infrastructure, and XR streaming mechanisms. It explains how different elements interact to deliver a seamless training experience while ensuring scalability, interoperability, and security.

Section 4 - Core features and Benefits of the XR5.0 Training Platform elaborates on the key functionalities that make the platform effective. It introduces the unified interface that allows users to access training programs easily, the centralised user and application management system that simplifies administration, and the XR streaming and device flexibility that ensures compatibility across various hardware. It also describes the platform’s approach to data security and compliance, its user analytics capabilities for tracking performance, and its resource scalability, which optimizes infrastructure utilisation. In addition, this section also highlights the features of XR material mapping, visualisation and personalised XR content.

Section 5 - Platform Deployment discusses how the system is integrated into real-world industrial settings. It outlines the deployment strategy, initial pilot applications, and how enterprises/pilots will implement the platform to improve workforce training. A short section on deploying the platform outside of the XR5.0 project is also addressed.

Finally, Section 6 - Conclusions & Future Work section summarizes the progress made in developing the XR5.0 Training Platform and provides insights into the next steps. It outlines the refinements and updates planned for Version 2, incorporating feedback from pilot deployments to enhance the platform’s capabilities.

2. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Extended Reality (XR) technologies, encompassing Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR), have demonstrated remarkable potential across a variety of industries. XR's ability to create immersive, interactive 3D environments enables users to engage with complex systems and processes in a simulated context, thereby fostering improved learning and skill development. However, despite its growing prominence in fields such as healthcare, surgery, aviation, and military training, the adoption of XR in industrial applications lags significantly behind. This disparity stems from several challenges unique to industrial contexts, as well as gaps in research and implementation strategies.

The Relevance of XR Technology in Industry

In industrial settings, XR technologies hold substantial promises for enhancing training programs and operational efficiency. Virtual environments (VEs), as a subset of XR, have been utilised to immerse trainees in realistic simulations, allowing them to practice skills and procedures in a controlled, risk-free environment [1][2]. Industries such as manufacturing, automotive, and service maintenance can leverage XR tools to replicate complex processes, enabling operators to acquire and refine procedural skills. These technologies can bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and hands-on experience by facilitating learning-by-doing approaches [3]. For instance, in the automotive sector, VEs are particularly relevant for training service operators. Modern vehicles often have numerous configurations—for example, luxury car models may feature up to 1,024 variations in engine, chassis, and electronic systems [4]. This complexity necessitates highly specialised training to ensure that operators can effectively diagnose and repair diverse systems. Furthermore, there is often a significant time lag between the introduction of a new car model and the occurrence of maintenance tasks, making it challenging for operators to retain procedural knowledge [5][6]. XR tools can address these challenges by enabling repeated practice in a virtual setting, ensuring operators are well-prepared when real-world tasks arise.

Despite the promise of XR technologies in industrial training, their adoption lags behind specialised fields like healthcare and aviation. Several factors contribute to this disparity, including limited research and standardization, which often focus only on basic performance metrics like error rates and task completion times rather than comprehensive proficiency measures [7][8][9]. The absence of standardized evaluation tools creates uncertainty about XR's long-term benefits in industry [10]. Additionally, skill decay—the gradual loss of proficiency over time—is rarely addressed, posing challenges in fields like automotive service where workers may not apply newly learned skills for months [11][12].

User-centric factors further affect the effectiveness of XR training, as individual differences in visuospatial abilities, learning styles, and trust in technology are often overlooked [13][14]. Task complexity and workload also play a role, as industrial training often involves managing significant cognitive and physical demands, yet their impact on performance and satisfaction remains inconsistently evaluated [15][16]. Additionally, usability issues such as cybersickness—a form of motion sickness caused by VR exposure—remain underreported, affecting trainees' comfort and engagement with XR applications [17].

To bridge these gaps, XR training programs should implement standardized evaluation tools to measure trainees' proficiency, retention, and satisfaction, facilitating more consistent assessments of XR's effectiveness [18][19]. Addressing skill decay through long-term studies and periodic refresher modules can help sustain proficiency. Incorporating user-centric design principles, such as accommodating diverse learning styles and cognitive abilities, can enhance usability and engagement. Furthermore, task design should balance complexity and workload while integrating real-time feedback to optimize learning. Reducing cybersickness through ergonomic improvements, latency minimization, and hardware design optimization is also crucial for increasing XR's effectiveness [20].

While XR holds great potential for improving operator performance and procedural knowledge, high implementation costs remain a barrier to widespread adoption [21]. Virtual environments (VEs) can be

more effective than traditional training in fostering skill acquisition and retention over time. However, industries must weigh the costs and benefits of virtual versus non-virtual training methods. By addressing gaps in research, standardization, and user experience, while developing cost-effective solutions such as cloud-based XR platforms, industries can unlock XR's full potential, paving the way for more efficient and effective training methodologies. [1][22].

Industry 5.0 and Operator 5.0

Industry 5.0 represents an evolution in industrial paradigms, emphasising the integration of human creativity and expertise with advanced technologies to foster human-centric, sustainable, and resilient manufacturing processes [23]. This approach seeks to address the limitations of Industry 4.0 by placing human well-being at the forefront of industrial development.

A core tenet of Industry 5.0 is the focus on human-centricity, which involves designing systems that prioritize human needs, values, and capabilities. This approach ensures that technology serves to enhance human roles rather than replace them, promoting collaboration between humans and machines. For instance, Collaborative Robots (COBOT) are designed to work alongside human operators, augmenting their capabilities and ensuring safety in shared workspaces. This synergy not only improves productivity but also enhances job satisfaction and worker well-being [24][25].

Industry 5.0 also emphasises sustainability and resilience, aiming to create production systems that are environmentally friendly and capable of withstanding disruptions. This involves adopting practices that minimize waste, optimize resource utilisation, and reduce energy consumption. The integration of advanced technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT), facilitates real-time monitoring and optimization of manufacturing processes, leading to more efficient and sustainable operations [26].

The ethical deployment of AI is a critical component of Industry 5.0. Trustworthy AI systems are designed to be transparent, fair, and aligned with human values, ensuring that their integration into industrial processes benefits society as a whole [27]. Moreover, Industry 5.0 supports the transition to a circular economy by promoting practices that extend product lifecycles, enable recycling and reuse, and reduce environmental impact [28]. This approach not only conserves resources but also fosters economic growth by creating new business opportunities in recycling and remanufacturing.

A significant aspect of Industry 5.0 is its focus on enhancing worker well-being. By leveraging human-centric design and advanced technologies, workplaces can be transformed to support the physical and mental health of employees. For example, ergonomic interventions supported by AI can help in designing workstations that reduce physical strain, while real-time monitoring systems can ensure safety and provide support in hazardous situations. This holistic approach leads to a more satisfied and productive workforce [29].

Operator 5.0 refers to the human workforce in this paradigm, empowered by advanced tools and technologies that enhance cognitive and physical capabilities. These operators collaborate with intelligent machines and systems, benefiting from tools like Extended Reality (XR), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and wearables to improve decision-making, reduce workload, and ensure safe operations [30]. Unlike traditional industrial roles, Operator 5.0 is not merely an executor of tasks but an adaptive and proactive problem solver, leveraging data-driven insights to optimize workflows. Human-machine collaboration is further enhanced through Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) and exoskeletons, which assist in high-precision tasks and physically demanding activities. This paradigm shift not only increases efficiency and productivity but also prioritizes worker well-being, reducing occupational hazards and cognitive overload [31][32].

Solutions for Industry 5.0 and Operator 5.0

Industry 5.0 solutions leverage Artificial Intelligence (AI) to create a more human-centric, efficient, and sustainable industrial landscape. Human-centric AI enhances decision-making by providing transparent and ethical insights, ensuring accountability and explainability in industrial applications [24]. Collaborative robotics (cobots) support human workers by handling repetitive or hazardous tasks, increasing productivity while reducing occupational risks [33]. Moreover, AI-driven process optimization improves production efficiency by optimizing workflows, reducing waste, and enhancing energy efficiency, aligning with Industry 5.0's sustainability goals [34][35].

Extended Reality (XR) plays a crucial role in empowering Operator 5.0 by bridging the gap between digital intelligence and human expertise. AR/VR-based training provides immersive and risk-free environments where operators can refine their skills, increasing competency and safety [36]. Real-time assistance through AR overlays enables operators to perform complex tasks with greater accuracy and efficiency, significantly reducing errors and cognitive load [37]. Additionally, XR-driven workplace ergonomics ensures optimized work environments, minimizing physical strain and improving overall well-being [38][39].

Digital twin technology further enhances Industry 5.0 by enabling real-time, data-driven decision-making and predictive analytics. Real-time monitoring of industrial assets through digital twins ensures continuous optimization and early fault detection, enhancing operational resilience [40]. Predictive maintenance, powered by AI and IoT, helps anticipate equipment failures, minimizing downtime and reducing maintenance costs [41]. Furthermore, scenario testing within digital twin environments allows manufacturers to simulate and refine processes before implementation, mitigating risks and ensuring efficiency [42]. These solutions collectively reinforce Industry 5.0's mission of integrating human expertise into intelligent systems for a more sustainable, productive, and worker-friendly industrial future.

XR training platforms in industry

Cloud-based XR platforms are revolutionizing industrial training by offering scalable, accessible, and customizable solutions. Hosting and streaming XR training applications through centralised repositories ensures seamless access across different locations and devices, enhancing flexibility and efficiency [43]. Secure cloud repositories for storage facilitate version control, collaborative access, and long-term archiving of training resources, ensuring consistency and reliability [44]. Additionally, authoring tools for training program creation empower trainers to develop immersive content using 3D assets, interactive scenarios, and assessments, even without advanced technical expertise [45]. These platforms also include collaboration features that enable multi-user environments, allowing trainees and instructors to interact in real time, fostering engagement and social learning [46]. Furthermore, data-driven insights derived from advanced analytics help assess training effectiveness, identify skill gaps, and track user engagement, ensuring continuous improvement and personalised learning experiences [47].

3. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

This section defines the architectural design of the XR5.0 Training Platform, outlining how its core components will be structured and integrated to ensure seamless operation. It details the key building blocks, their interactions, and the technical infrastructure required for deployment. The subsections cover the overall system architecture, individual components, integration strategy, and technical requirements, providing a blueprint for how the platform will be developed and implemented.

3.1 Architecture

This section details the system architecture of a cloud-based XR streaming platform, highlighting its significance in transforming industrial training. XR streaming platforms provide immersive learning environments that enhance skill acquisition, operational efficiency, and workforce engagement. By integrating advanced technologies like Extended Reality (XR), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Cloud Computing, Orchestration, and GUI-driven management, these platforms address the challenges of scalability, usability, and real-time interaction.

The XR5.0 Training Platform is a cloud-based XR training and streaming platform that will enable Industry 5.0 operators to be able to run XR training applications on-demand specific to selected industrial scenarios within the I5.0 ecosystem. The end-users or operators will be able to leverage the training platform to undergo immersive training in AR/VR mode with real-time interactions. The platform is based on HOLO's enterprise streaming platform Hololight Hub, which in-itself is an XR platform for hosting, managing and collating enterprise XR applications (T5.3).

The platform will provide a cloud repository (T5.2), developed by partner SYN, that will enable industrial enterprises to upload and store their training materials and assets. The repository will be integrated with the XR platform to enable streaming of XR training assets in real-time to end-users. In addition, XR5.0 training platform will offer the industrial enterprise the functionality to design and develop immersive training programs (T5.1 & T5.4), developed by partner IML, that will address the needs of various operators based on expertise and level in industrial environments in alignment with XR5.0 pilots and use cases. As a result, it will enable industrial operators to be completely immersed during training sessions in a high-quality and robust virtual environment grounded in a real-world industrial context. Furthermore, the platform will be designed in compliance with GDPR, ensuring data protection through secure storage, access control, encryption, and user consent mechanisms.

The XR5.0 Training Platform has been developed and designed in accordance with the reference architecture and technical specifications described in deliverable D2.2 – “Reference Architecture Model and Technical Specifications” written with WP2.

Figure 3 details the system architecture of the XR5.0 Training Platform, designed for hosting and streaming XR applications to end devices. The platform supports administrative operations through web browsers and delivers XR experiences to operators via XR devices, such as AR/VR headsets. The architecture ensures seamless management of applications and users, robust orchestration of cloud resources, and efficient XR content delivery.

Figure 3 - XR5.0 Training Platform Architecture

The core components of the XR5.0 streaming platform form the foundation of its robust and scalable functionality. Each component plays a critical role in ensuring seamless delivery of high-quality XR content, efficient management of applications and users, and optimal utilisation of cloud resources. Below is a detailed breakdown of the platform’s key components, emphasising their significance and interconnectedness in the system architecture.

- Graphical User Interface (GUI) - The GUI plays a pivotal role in enhancing user experience and ensuring seamless interaction between administrators and operators. It serves as the primary point of engagement for both user groups, offering tailored and personalised functionalities to meet their specific needs.
 - Web Browser: Through an intuitive and centralised dashboard, administrators and managers can efficiently oversee XR applications, training programs and user activity. This includes deploying and updating applications, creating and uploading training programs and monitoring user activity, and analysing application performance. The GUI through a unified interface enables quick decision-making and effective resource management.
 - XR Device Interface: For operators, the GUI translates complex industrial training scenarios into immersive and interactive experiences in XR. Operators interact with a custom client application on any XR device such as Microsoft HoloLens 2 or Meta Quest 3 to access XR applications and training programs assigned to them. Furthermore, it ensures smooth content delivery and real-time interaction with XR content and training modules for the users.
- Platform Services: The services layer constitutes the backbone of the XR5.0 Training Platform’s functionalities. This component is integral to maintaining platform efficiency, security, and user satisfaction by enabling seamless and unified management and interaction across the system. The platform services include the below services, which are described in detail in Section 3.2.
 - Hololight Hub: A streaming platform that forms the backbone of the XR5.0 Training Platform as it is used to manage, host and stream the XR applications.
 - XR Asset Repository: Essentially the file storage system of the platform. It stores all the

training materials and assets as well as training programs uploaded by the admin. SYN are developing and designing the repository for the XR5.0 project.

- XR Training Management System: A system to enable admins to create immersive step-by-step training programs dedicated to specific I5.0 training scenarios.

HOLO will deploy its enterprise XR platform (Hololight Hub), customizing it to align with XR5.0 project's specific requirements. Concurrently, Partners SYN and IML will develop novel solutions from the ground up (XR Asset Repository & Training Programs Authoring Tool), ensuring that the project integrates cutting-edge advancements. Collectively, the contributions of all three partners drive the platform's overall innovation.

- Virtualisation Provider: Amazon Web Services (AWS) serves as the virtualisation provider for the XR5.0 Training Platform, offering the computational infrastructure necessary to host and execute high-performance XR applications. By leveraging AWS's robust cloud computing capabilities, the platform ensures scalability, reliability, and seamless operation of resource-intensive XR applications. The XR5.0 Training Platform via Hololight Hub commands the virtualisation provider to provide a virtual environment (high-performance VMs equipped with GPUs) to deploy and run the XR application.
 - XR Applications: XR5.0-enabled XR applications that are developed as part of WP6 are hosted on Hololight Hub and run in VMs provided by AWS. These applications are built using Unity³, a widely used game engine, and communicate with external services such as the Human-Centric Digital Twin (HDT) and AI models (AL, NSAI, GenAI) via APIs or other communication protocols. The HDT incorporates personalization and human factors, adapting training experiences based on user profiles, preferences, and role/skill. Both the Digital Twin and AI models are developed in compliance with GDPR regulations, ensuring data privacy and security, thereby ensuring that the XR application also adheres to these standards. This integration is handled within the application logic and the applications are built with the following Unity-based plugins:
 - Hololight Stream - used to enable XR application streaming from the cloud to XR end-devices.
 - XR Repository Plugin - used to download files such as 3D models from the cloud repository storage into the XR environment.
 - XR Training Plugin - used to download the training programs developed using the web browser into the XR environment.

3.2 Components

The following section discusses and describes the building blocks of the XR5.0 Training Platform.

3.2.1 Hololight Hub

Hololight Hub⁴, developed by HOLO, is a cloud-based system that hosts, manages, and streams XR applications in real time to devices from the cloud ensuring high-quality, low latency streaming, enabling smooth experiences regardless of device capabilities. Features like application version control, user management, analytics, and robust security protocols make it an efficient solution for industrial training.

³ <https://unity.com/>

⁴ <https://hololight.com/products/hololight-hub-xr-streaming-platform/>

By centralizing XR application management, organizations can quickly update their content and provide access to users across multiple locations, simplifying operations while enhancing scalability.

Hololight Hub, deployed in the XR5.0 project as the backbone of the XR5.0 Training Platform, uses Amazon Web Services (AWS)⁵ cloud infrastructure to orchestrate and run XR5.0 apps, leveraging Hololight Stream⁶, a remote rendering solution for immersive, lag-free and secure XR streaming.

Figure 4 - Hololight Hub Microservices Architecture

Figure 4 illustrates the architecture of the Hololight Hub web services framework within the XR5.0 Training Platform, with emphasis on centralised application and user management. The system follows a microservices-based architecture, ensuring modularity, scalability, and efficient management of applications, users, and resources. The key architectural components and their functions are described below:

i. API Gateway

The API Gateway acts as the central interface through which XR devices, and the web browsers communicate with the XR5.0 Training Platform’s backend services. The main functions of the API Gateway include:

- directs incoming requests to appropriate microservices (user management, application management, analytics etc.).
- ensures secure access by verifying user credentials and permissions (authentication and authorization) before allowing access to sensitive resources (XR apps, training material, files etc.).

⁵ <https://aws.amazon.com/>

⁶ <https://hololight.com/products/hololight-stream-xr-streaming-sdk/>

ii. Microservices Layer

The following microservices have been designed for the XR5.0 Training Platform:

- User Management
 - handles authentication, user roles, and access control for tenants, admins and end-users.
 - ensures Single Sign-On (SSO) authentication through an SSO provider (OAuth 2.0) allowing seamless login across the platform.
 - manages Role-based Access Control (RBAC) for different users (tenants, admins, end-users).
- Application Management
 - facilitates centralised deployment, version control and distribution of XR5.0 applications.
 - enables tenant-specific configurations, ensuring that each organization (Pilot Leader - KUKA, EKS0 etc.) can customize application settings as required.
 - simplifies application updates, eliminating the need for users to manually download new versions as it is following a streaming-based deployment.
- Usage Analytics
 - collects data on user activity, session duration, application usage, usage region and performance metrics.
 - provides real-time insights to tenant admins and platform managers, aiding in resource optimization and training performance improvements.
 - supports decision-making by identifying trends in user engagement and application effectiveness.
- Orchestration (instance management)
 - manages resource allocation and deployment of XR5.0 applications on the AWS cloud infrastructure.
 - ensure scalability by dynamically provisioning computing resources based on demand.

iii. External Services & Infrastructure

The following external services have been designed for the XR5.0 Training Platform:

- SSO Provider
 - facilitates secure, seamless login for users across different devices and interfaces.
- Database
 - stores user profiles, tenant data, and application configurations.
 - ensures data isolation per tenant, following strict access control mechanisms.

- Cloud (AWS – Virtualisation and Compute Resources)
 - executes XR applications, ensuring they run efficiently on cloud-based virtual machines (EC2 instances).
 - supports High-Performance Computing (HPC) for rendering and streaming XR applications to remote devices.

Interaction Workflow (Figure 5):

Figure 5 - Microservices Interaction Workflow

3.2.2 XR Training Asset Repository

3.2.2.1. Owncloud-based Storage/File Sharing

Owncloud⁷ is an open-source file-sharing platform. It was selected as the basis of the XR Training Assets Repository due to its extensive customization options and its focus on security because of the sensitive nature of all forms of training in corporate environments. It’s also highly scalable and can work with minimal resources during prototype development. The XR Training Asset Repository is developed by SYN via Owncloud.

3.2.2.2. XR Training Repository WebApp

The Training Repository WebApp functions as a mediator between the other components of the Training Platform (Hololight Hub, XR Training Management System) and the underlying storage provided by Owncloud. It provides interfaces for Application, Training Module, Resource, Asset, Sharing and User management. Since most of the Interfaces are going to be invoked by other components, they are all implemented as Web APIs, with no GUI, other than a Swagger Instance, although one is planned for the final release as part of the Unified Interface.

- Application Management Interface - It allows the allocation of storage for an XR Application (hosted in Hololight Hub) and the association between the Application and Training Modules/Programs, Resources, and Assets (created by the XR Training Management System). Figure 6 illustrates the management interface.

⁷ <https://owncloud.com/>

- User Management Interface - Allocates storage space in OwnCloud for users created for a tenant in the Hololight Hub and handles permissions/security based on their status (admin or not, group participation).
- Training Module/Resource/Asset Management Interface - Allocates storage for a Training Module/Resource/Asset. Generally, Assets are stored as files, while Resources are directories containing Assets and other Resources(subdirectories). Refer to Figure 7.
- Share Management Interface - Allows administrators to share Modules/Resources/Bundles with other users. It allows sharing based on group participation or individually. The sharing can be read only or in full control. Generally, for security reasons, non-administrative users only have access to files explicitly shared with them. Refer to Figure 8.

Figure 6 - Application Management Interface

Figure 7 - Sample Training Module Comprising two assets (PDF& PNG files) and a Resource Bundle

Figure 8 - Sharing an Asset with a User

3.2.2.3. Repository Plugin (XRRP)

The Repository plugin provides the XR Application Developers with a library aiming to assist them in interacting with the XR Training Repository in a seamless manner. It interfaces with the WebApp to receive information about available training modules, resources & assets and with the Owncloud instance to allow the downloading of the training assets. Figure 9 and Figure 10 show the Repository Plugin in XR environment.

Figure 9 - Navigating a training module with the Repository Plugin

Figure 10 - Downloading and displaying an image asset

Currently, the training plugin supports only the visualisation of basic asset types (text files, JSON & images). More complex asset types will be handled by the XR Training plugin developed as part of the XR Training Management System.

3.2.3 XR Training Management System

The XR Training Management System, developed by IML, is a comprehensive component within the XR5.0 Training Platform to support the creation, management, and display of XR Training Materials and Programs for a wide range of contexts and use cases of industrial training. It consists of two main components:

1. Training Programs Authoring Tool (TPAT): Web application for managers to create and manage XR Training Programs and Materials.
2. XR Training Plugin (XRTP): Unity plugin that enables the visualisation of XR Training Programs and Materials in XR devices.

Figure 11 - Diagram illustrating the interaction between components of the XR Training Management System

3.2.3.1. Training Programs Authoring Tool (TPAT)

The TPAT enables the creation and management of XR Training Programs and Materials. XR Training Materials are materials designed for the immersive nature of XR environments. These offer suitable visualisations for XR, making learning content easier to engage with. XR Training Programs organise materials into task-focused modules. They offer clear structure and defined goals tailored to user profiles and needs.

The TPAT (Figure 12) includes the following modules: i) Training Content Gateway; ii) XR Material Authoring Toolkit; iii) XR Content Generator; iv) XR Training Materials Manager; v) XR Training Programs Manager; vi) XR Training API.

Figure 12 - Diagram illustrating the interaction between modules of the TPAT

i. Training Content Gateway

This module enables users to upload new training content or select from existing resources. It integrates with the XR Training Asset Repository component to deliver functionality within the TPAT. It currently supports PDFs, images and videos, but discussions are underway to extend support to 3D models and e-learning standards (ex. SCORM packages). Refer to Figure 13 and Figure 14.

Figure 13 - Managers can upload training content by selecting the 'Upload file' tab in the asset selection box

Figure 14 - Managers can select existing training content by selecting the 'Asset Library' tab in the asset selection box

ii. XR Material Authoring Toolkit

This module offers tools to adapt traditional training content into XR Training Materials. It currently provides manual processes, but discussions are underway to integrate AI-powered features.

Managers can currently extract text and images manually from PDFs (Figure 15, Figure 16). AI-powered features are currently under discussion to enhance this process. Two features are being evaluated: content extraction; content generation. The content extraction will enable automated extraction and content formatting using text prompts. The content generation feature will provide suggestions to assist in the creation of XR Training Materials.

Figure 15 - Managers can extract text from PDFs and generate checklists or workflows

Figure 16 - Managers can extract images from PDFs using the snip tool

As mentioned before, support for 3D models is under discussion. Two features are currently under evaluation: exploded views and a workflow builder. The exploded views will help generate detailed breakdown of 3D models. The workflow builder will enable the configuration of 3D models into step-by-step workflows.

iii. XR Content Generator

This module, currently under discussion, will automate the generation of XR Training Materials and Programs from traditional training content. From a single asset, a manager will be able to automatically generate one or more XR compatible versions. This feature will enable automated and bulk content generation to streamline the content creation process.

iv. XR Training Materials Manager

This module allows the creation and linking of XR Training Materials. Managers can either create these materials from scratch, adapt traditional training content, or generate new content using the XR Content Generator module. Managers can also link related materials to create a network of interconnected content. This network enhances the learning experience by providing easy access to relevant, related resources.

At the time of writing this deliverable, TPAT currently supports the following XR Training Materials: Checklists; Images; Videos; Workflows.

Checklists enable the creation of items list to support operators during tasks. Managers can create checklists from scratch or using extracted content from PDFs (Figure 17). Also, they can link checklist items to a set of related materials to provide extra content.

Figure 17 - Managers can create checklist items with additional description and related materials

Images and Videos provide multimedia content visualisation in XR. Managers can upload image files or extract them from PDFs. In the case of Videos, they can only upload video files. In both cases, managers can enhance the materials with annotations. Video annotations (Figure 18) are currently supported, with image annotations planned for future implementation. Also, they can link each annotation to a set of related materials, making it a part of the content network.

Figure 18 - Managers can create video chapters and annotations with a set of related materials

Workflows provide step-by-step sequential instructions to guide operators. Each workflow step will include a customizable page that allows advanced text formatting to craft content for optimal presentation (Figure 19). Also, each step can be linked to a set of related materials providing extra content. Like checklists, workflows can be created from scratch or by extracting content from PDFs.

The screenshot displays the 'Steps' configuration interface. On the left, a sidebar lists 'Workflow', 'Details', 'Steps', and 'Materials'. The main content area is titled 'Steps' and features two buttons: 'New Step' and 'Extract'. Below these is a form for 'Step 1', which includes a 'Title' input field, a 'Content' field with a rich text editor (containing the text 'This is test editor content'), and a 'Related Materials' section. The 'Related Materials' section has a 'Material Title' input field and an 'Add Material' button. At the bottom left of the sidebar, there are 'Save' and 'Cancel' buttons.

Figure 19 - Managers can create workflow steps with formatted text for optimal presentation

Under discussion for XR Training Materials is the ability to create AI assistants that will support operators within the XR environment. These assistants have natural language understanding, enabling intuitive interactions using conversational language. Operators can ask questions about the training materials and receive contextual, relevant answers.

v. XR Training Programs Manager

This module allows the creation and management of XR Training Programs. Currently, managers create these programs from scratch, but automated processes are in discussion. A proposed feature is the ability to generate training programs from e-learning standards (ex. SCORM).

An XR Training Program consists of the program metadata and content (Figure 20). The program metadata currently includes the program's name, description, learning objectives, and requirements. This list will expand to include user-specific parameters for targeting and personalisation. The program content includes the associated XR Training Materials. Managers can associate relevant materials to each training program. In a later stage, they will be able to organise the materials in a logical sequence to create a structured learning path. Crafting a coherent learning path is essential to encourage progressive skill development.

The screenshot shows a web application interface for managing training programs. On the left, a vertical sidebar contains the menu items 'Program', 'Details', and 'Materials', with 'Program' currently selected. Below the sidebar are two buttons: a purple 'Save' button and a red 'Cancel' button. The main content area is titled 'Details' and contains four text input fields, each with a 'Write a message' placeholder. The fields are labeled 'Title', 'Description', 'Objectives', and 'Requirements'. Below the 'Details' section is a 'Materials' section. It features a search bar with a magnifying glass icon and the text 'Search', a dropdown menu labeled 'Filter', and a purple 'Add Material' button. Below these elements is a table with one row. The table header is 'Material Title' and the data cell contains the text 'Metadata: Author, date, published, category, difficulty level, etc'.

Figure 20 - Managers can create Training Programs with metadata and associated Training Materials

An essential feature of this module, currently under discussion at the time of writing this deliverable, is the assessment configuration. This feature will enable the integration of assessment activities in the learning flow. These activities will be crucial for assessing the knowledge and skills acquired during the program and will offer important insights into the program's effectiveness.

vi. XR Training API

This module enables access to the XR Training Programs and Materials from external platforms. It allows retrieving programs and associated materials for visualisation. Currently used by the XRTP, this module will also allow integration with other systems.

3.2.3.2. XR Training Plugin (XRTP)

This component enables the visualisation of XR Training Programs and Materials in XR devices. It works in tandem with the TPAT to deliver immersive interfaces to engage with the training content. It's distributed as a Unity plugin to enable the integration in third-party Unity XR apps.

The XRTP (Figure 21) includes the following modules: i) Training Data Service; ii) Training Interface Toolkit; iii) Training Program Manager; iv) Virtual Dashboard System; v) Adaptive Interface Engine.

Figure 21 - Diagram illustrating the interaction between modules of the XRTP

i. Training Data Service

This module handles communication with external services to retrieve training data. Currently, it communicates with the API module of the TPAT to access the training content. It will also support integration with other systems as long as the data is in the appropriate format.

ii. Training Interface Toolkit

This module provides immersive interfaces for displaying XR Training Materials, optimized for XR environments to deliver an intuitive experience. They support hand interaction and anchoring within the virtual space. Operators can customize the interface positions for optimal visualisation and comfort. Although not currently supported, features such as scaling and gaze-based interactions are being considered for future implementation.

This module currently supports the following XR Training Materials: Checklists; Images; Videos; Workflows. Each interface supports the unique features of each material but also shared functionalities. As discussed in the XR Training Materials Management module of the TPAT, each material can be linked to a set of related ones. Each interface provides access to linked materials in a standardized location, common to all.

Figure 22 showcases the Checklist Viewer. It displays a list of toggleable items and linked materials. In the top left corner, the operator can access materials linked to the checklist. To the right of each list item, materials linked to that item are also accessible.

Figure 22 - Screenshot of the Checklist Viewer displaying related training materials associated with both the Checklist and individual Checklist Items

Figure 23 showcases the Image Viewer. It displays an image with zoom options, for a more detailed visualisation. It currently does not support image annotations, but this feature is planned for future implementation.

Figure 23 - Screenshot of the Image Viewer

Figure 24 showcases the Video Player. It displays a video with standard playback controls, chapters and annotations. Chapters allow operators to quickly navigate between video sections, improving efficiency. Annotations provide access to additional information and linked materials at specific points in the video.

Figure 24 - Screenshot of the Training Video Player showcasing the Chapters and Annotation features

Figure 25 shows the Workflow Viewer. It displays a main content area along with page navigation controls for a step-by-step navigation between workflow steps. Each step content page supports basic text formatting options and includes a set of linked materials.

Figure 25 - Screenshot of the Workflow Viewer showcasing content formatting and related materials linked to a specific Workflow Step

iii. Training Program Manager

This module enables access to the XR Training Programs. It displays the training data obtained from the Training Data Service. Operators can check the available training programs as well as their metadata and content.

The module is currently composed of three interfaces: Program List Viewer, Program Metadata Viewer, and Program Content Viewer. These interfaces support the current training program definition but will be updated to align with the planned changes discussed earlier on the XR Training Programs Manager module of TPAT.

Figure 26 showcases the Program List Viewer. It displays a list of the training programs operators have access to. Operators can either start a program or navigate to the Program Metadata Viewer for additional information. Extra searching and filtering functionalities are under discussion.

Figure 26 - Screenshot of the Programs List Viewer displaying a list of training programs

Figure 27 showcases the Program Metadata Viewer. It displays the selected training program's details, including the description, objectives, and requirements. Operators can choose to start the program or go back to the previous list.

Figure 27 - Screenshot of the Program Metadata Viewer displaying detailed information about a training program

Figure 28 showcases the Program Content Viewer. At the time of writing this deliverable, it displays a list of associated XR Training Materials. The interface will evolve to display the sequence and progress, guiding the operator through the learning process. Operators can access each training material, displayed through the interfaces described in the previous module.

Figure 28 - Screenshot of the Program Content Viewer showing a sequence of associated training materials

iv. Virtual Dashboard System

This module, planned for future implementation, will provide a system for view management in virtual spaces. It will enable easier placement of views in space, along with the ability to manage their state. Operators can dock views in predefined spaces for better organization and accessibility. They can also minimize views to reduce clutter and enhance focus. A focus mode is also being considered, where it dims views and the environment to highlight a single view.

v. Adaptive Interface Engine

This module, currently under discussion, will provide an adaptive interface tailored to the operator's profile. By combining user interaction data with profile information, the interface will dynamically adjust to improve efficiency and usability.

3.3 Integration of Components

The XR5.0 Training Platform is built upon three core services: Hololight Hub for web services and orchestration, XR Training Asset Repository, and the XR Training Management System, all working together to ensure seamless XR training content delivery, user management, and system scalability. A key aspect of this integration is Single Sign-On (SSO), ensuring secure and unified user authentication across the platform.

3.3.1 Architectural Overview of Component Integration

The XR5.0 Training Platform employs a microservices-based architecture, ensuring modularity and scalability. Each core function, such as user management, application deployment, and training content delivery, operates as an independent service while communicating through a centralised API gateway.

Integration strategies include:

- **API-Driven Communication:** Standardized APIs enable seamless interoperability between components, ensuring modular integration.
- **Cloud-Centric Data Exchange:** Training materials, XR assets, and metadata are dynamically retrieved from the XR Asset Repository based on user roles and permissions.
- **Event-Driven Orchestration:** Resource allocation and synchronization between components are managed through event-based triggers, optimizing system performance and reducing latency.

3.3.2 Component-Level Integration

At the core, Hololight Hub layer handles authentication, access control, and training session management. Through SSO integration, users authenticate once using enterprise credentials, gaining access to the platform without needing multiple logins. This authentication process is managed via an Identity Provider (IdP), which verifies user credentials and grants appropriate access levels. Once authenticated, the Web Services layer orchestrates interactions between users, XR5.0 applications, and training content. The XR Asset Repository stores all training materials, including 3D models, documents, and multimedia files. The Training Program Authoring Tool dynamically retrieves these resources based on user permissions, ensuring access to the correct training materials.

- **Training Program Management and XR Asset Repository** - Upon logging in via SSO, the admin gains access to the platform's management interface, where they can add users, upload training materials to the repository, and manage XR5.0 applications. Using the Training Programs Authoring Tool, the admin creates XR training programs and stores them in the XR Asset Repository, ensuring that all content is centrally available. The admin can also upload XR applications and assign them to specific users. The platform supports:

- Role-Based Access Control (RBAC): Ensures users only access assigned training content.
- Automatic Synchronization: Updates are propagated across all connected devices without requiring manual downloads.
- Version Control & Metadata Storage: Tracks content revisions and maintains structured training records.
- XR Asset Management and Device Orchestration - When a user/operator logs in from an XR device, they authenticate via SSO and access the assigned applications. The selected XR app retrieves relevant training materials and programs from the XR Asset Repository using Unity-based plugins. To execute the training session, the Hololight Hub component dynamically provides an AWS EC2 instance, streaming the XR application to the user's device via Hololight Stream. Key integration mechanisms include:
 - Unity-Based Plugins: XR applications retrieve training materials and training programs directly from the XR Asset Repository.
 - Real-Time Streaming Infrastructure: Reduces hardware dependency by rendering content in the cloud and streamed via Hololight Stream.
 - Dynamic Resource Allocation: The orchestration engine scales compute resources based on real-time user demand.

This integration ensures secure access control, efficient content management, and dynamic resource allocation, enabling a robust and scalable XR training experience. Further refinements will be made to optimize orchestration, authentication flows, and streaming performance as development progresses. These components are designed to work in a tightly integrated manner, allowing enterprises to deliver scalable and efficient training experiences. While the high-level architecture is defined, specific integration mechanisms, data flow, and API interactions between these services are still being refined at the time of writing this deliverable and will be detailed in the next version of this deliverable D5.4.

3.4 Technical Requirements

The following outlines the key technical requirements for the platform.

1. Infrastructure Requirements

- Cloud Compute & Storage: The platform relies on AWS EC2 instances for XR application streaming and storage for XR applications.
 - i. Web Services & Orchestration - 4vCPUs, 2 GB RAM, 100 GB Storage
 - ii. Cloud Compute (AWS EC2) - Instances used for XR streaming - g4dn.4xlarge (for GPU acceleration), g6.4xlarge. OS - Windows Server 2019.
 - iii. Cloud Storage (AWS S3): No storage limits. Used for file system and application storage.
- Networking & Latency Optimization: Low-latency connections via WebRTC-based streaming ensure smooth XR experiences.
- Scalability & Load Balancing: Dynamic provisioning of EC2 instances based on user demand ensures resource efficiency.

2. Security and Authentication

- Single Sign-On (SSO): Integrates OAuth 2.0 support for user authentication, ensuring secure access.
- Role-Based Access Control (RBAC): Admins can manage user permissions for training materials and XR applications.

3. XR Device and Application

- Device Compatibility: The XR5.0 Training Platform supports Microsoft HoloLens 2, Meta Quest 2/3/Pro, Magic Leap 2, Apple iPad/iPhone and Lenovo VFX through a Unity-based client.
- Streaming Protocols: WebRTC-based rendering via Hololight Stream ensures high-performance, low-latency streaming from the cloud to XR devices.
- XR Applications:
 - i. OS - Windows
 - ii. Game Engine - Unity
 - iii. Plugin Integration - The application must be built with the following Unity-based plugins - Hololight Stream SDK, XR Asset Repository Plugin and XR Training Plugin.

4. Hardware Requirements

- XR device: The XR5.0 Training Platform can be accessed through a device-specific version of the client application running on the XR device since the high-performance rendering servers are automatically started in the cloud.

5. Network & Security Protocols

- Hololight Stream: Stream uses WebRTC protocol wherein data is transmitted securely with Secure Real-time Transport Protocol (SCTP) and Datagram Transport Layer Security (DTLS).
- Login, Application Loading, Querying, Signalling: HTTPS protocol.
- Bandwidth requirements - Table 1.

Table 1 - Hololight Stream Bandwidth Requirements

	Minimum	Recommended
Network	Wi-Fi 5GHz	Wi-Fi 5GHz
Bandwidth	20 Mbit	40 Mbit
Round Trip Time (Latency)	-	max. 50ms

These technical requirements ensure that the XR5.0 Training Platform remains scalable, secure, and adaptable to industrial training needs. Since the platform is in the early design phase at the time of writing this deliverable, specifications may evolve based on further development, testing, and real-world validation.

4. CORE FEATURES AND BENEFITS OF THE XR5.0 TRAINING PLATFORM

The following section outlines the core features and expected benefits of the XR5.0 Training Platform as envisioned for the project's duration. While these features are still in development at the time of this deliverable, they are designed to be fully implemented and operational by the project's conclusion.

4.1 Industrial Training through a Unified Interface

The XR5.0 Training Platform is designed to offer a centralised and intuitive interface that streamlines industrial training by integrating all essential tools and services into a single environment that will address the needs of different industrial operators across expertise and position in various industrial environments. This unified interface will allow administrators, trainers, and operators to seamlessly manage training programs, XR5.0 applications, and user access without navigating between multiple systems.

Figure 29 illustrates the mock-up of a web browser that the admin/manager will access. Through the XR5.0 Training Platform web interface, the admin will be able to:

- manage XR applications and the devices they wish to support under the 'Applications' tab
- manage training materials and assets under the 'XR Asset Repository' tab
- create step-by-step training workflows under the 'Training Programs Authoring Tool' tab
- manage and analyse user sessions and have a complete overview of the platform usage under the 'User Management' tab

Figure 29 - Admin View/Web Browser mock-up interface - The remote expert/admin utilises a web interface to upload and manage applications, training material, assets and users

Similarly, the XR5.0 Training Platform ensures a seamless and user-friendly experience by providing a single, intuitive interface to access the XR5.0 Training Platform through the XR devices. Figure 30 illustrates the mock-up of the client application on the XR device. The client application on the XR device presents users with a dashboard view, displaying the training applications available to them under the 'Applications' tab. On a web browser, users can easily view their session history and analyse their training activity and engagement, ensuring continuity in their learning process. By selecting an application from this view, users can launch their desired training application instantly.

Figure 30 - User View mock-up on Client App: On the XR device, trainees/users can access a library of XR applications specifically assigned to them. Depending on the context of their task or training, they can select and run the appropriate application from this library.

Once the XR5.0 application is launched, the user sees the UI of the XR5.0 application selected on the XR device as illustrated in Figure 31 enabling the user to:

- access the training programs assigned to the user by the admin under the ‘Training Programs’ tab
- access the training materials such as 3D models and pdfs under the ‘Files’ tab

Figure 31 - User View mock-up on Pilot XR App: On the XR device, trainees/users can access the training programs, and the training assets/files specifically assigned to them. Depending on the context of their task or training, they can select and run the appropriate training.

By consolidating application management, user administration, training material storage, training program creation and user analytics, the platform simplifies complex workflows ensuring a more efficient training process. The interface is designed for ease of use, featuring Role-based Access Control, enabling different user types—such as enterprise administrators, training managers, and trainees—to interact with relevant features based on their permissions. By offering a cohesive and interactive training experience, the platform enhances usability, minimizes onboarding time, and maximizes training efficiency across various Industry 5.0 applications.

4.2 Centralised Application and User Management

Centralised application and user management is pivotal to ensure efficient resource allocation, tenant isolation, and administrative control. Hence, for a scalable and efficient application and user management, the XR5.0 Training Platform adopts a multi-tenant architecture that focuses on centralised management while maintaining high levels of customization and security for each tenant.

Multi-tenant architecture, illustrated in Figure 32, enables multiple organizations, or tenants, to share a single software instance while keeping their data and configurations isolated. In this setup a centralised system ensures clear boundaries between tenants, enabling each to manage its resources, users, and applications independently. Each tenant’s data and configurations are logically separated, ensuring privacy and customisation without duplicating the underlying infrastructure.

Figure 32 - Multi-Tenant Architecture for XR5.0 Training Platform user management

The key roles and their responsibilities are described in Table 2.

Table 2 - Key roles in the multi-tenant architecture

Key Role	Responsibilities	XR5.0 Relevance
Tenant Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oversee the platform and platform-wide settings. Manage Tenants - add/remove 	HOLO will be the tenant manager.

Tenant (single owner)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assign one or more Admins to oversee operations within the tenancy. 	Pilot Leaders such as KUKA (Pilot 1, T6.2) and EKSO (Pilot 3, T6.4) will be added as tenants.
Admin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manage multiple apps in a centralised location and can provide access to select users based on role and skill. Admins can select the XR devices they wish to support. 	Tenants or Pilot Leaders add managers/experts as administrators who manage users, apps, and resources within their domain.
Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use the applications and training content (training assets and programs) assigned to them on the XR device. 	Operators and participants belonging to the end-user (Pilot Leader - KUKA, EKSO, TAP etc.) who access the XR apps and the training content.

Admin and User Workflows are illustrated in Figure 33 and Figure 34.

Figure 33 - Example admin workflow

Figure 34 - Example user workflow

Application Management: Simplified Application Update Cycle

One of the key advantages of the centralised XR5.0 Training Platform is the streamlined application update process. Traditionally, updating applications require individual users or devices to download and install the latest versions, which could lead to delays, version mismatches, and administrative overhead. With the centralised architecture of this XR platform, the process becomes significantly easier. The admin uploads the updated version of the XR application to the Hololight Hub layer on the XR5.0 Training Platform via the management dashboard (refer to Figure 35). This eliminates the need for tenant admins or end users to manually manage updates. Once uploaded, the updated application is streamed directly to client devices. This ensures that all users access the latest version instantly without requiring local installations or

downloads. The elimination of manual updates reduces maintenance burdens on IT staff and ensures version uniformity across the platform. Users always interact with the most up-to-date application, minimizing errors caused by outdated versions and users can continue training sessions without lengthy interruptions, as the update process is seamless and transparent.

Figure 35 - Application Upload Process

4.3 XR Streaming & Device-Agnostic Approach

The Hologlight Stream Software Development Kit (SDK) is a remote rendering solution that enables real-time streaming of entire Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) applications. By streaming entire applications, Hologlight Stream enables visualisation and interaction with highly polygonal, data-intensive content such as graphics-intensive 3D objects and Computer-Aided Design (CAD) models, which would otherwise be unlikely on native applications due to the limitation in the processing power of the Extended Reality (XR) devices.

Figure 36 - Hologlight Stream is a remote rendering SDK that lets you run your Unity-built XR application on a powerful workstation, local server, or cloud-based infrastructure

Engineers/Developers can integrate Hologlight Stream SDK (Figure 36) into any Unity-based XR application. Its multi-device support and native Unity 3D integration streamline application development, saving time and effort while increasing the security and scalability of AR and VR applications. With Hologlight Stream, users can run their Unity-built XR application on a powerful workstation, local server, or cloud-based infrastructure. The client app sends data - sensor data for room tracking, head pose, audio stream, gesture input, SLAM - to the cloud server. After the data is processed on the cloud server, the rendered images are encoded to use less network traffic and sent back to the client app, where they are decoded again. This enables the secure streaming of applications to all major AR or VR headsets and iOS devices on the market to visualise high-fidelity content without down-sampling data.

With Hologlight Stream technology, the XR5.0 Training Platform eliminates the traditional device compatibility challenges that IT teams face, ensuring seamless operation across different hardware configurations. In conventional setups, enterprises must frequently reconfigure servers, address

compatibility issues, and manage hardware limitations, leading to operational inefficiencies and increased downtime. The platform's server-side management approach resolves these issues by shifting the computational workload away from the end device, allowing effortless adaptability to different hardware generations.

Unlike traditional training solutions where devices have limited lifespans and quickly become obsolete, the XR5.0 Training Platform ensures device-agnostic operation. The system's built-in streaming technology, Hologlight Stream, ensures that as long as a device has an internet connection, it can access and run XR applications without performance degradation. This eliminates the need for costly hardware upgrades and extends the usability of existing devices, allowing enterprises to maximize return on investment while maintaining high training efficiency.

Administrators can easily add or remove devices through a centralised management interface, ensuring that organizations can scale their XR training solutions without logistical constraints. This flexibility is particularly valuable in dynamic industrial environments where new devices are introduced frequently. The platform's cloud-based infrastructure also enables IT teams to deploy software updates and application improvements centrally, without requiring manual intervention on each device. This streamlined update process reduces maintenance overhead and ensures that all users always have access to the latest versions of training applications. The platform supports various devices enabling enterprises to select the device that best aligns with their specific use cases as well as adapting to device capabilities while offering other device features like spatial mapping, hand and eye tracking for enhanced XR experiences.

By eliminating device-dependent constraints, the XR5.0 Training Platform ensures that enterprises can seamlessly adapt to evolving technology trends, support a diverse range of hardware, and maintain a future-proof training environment (refer to Table 3). This maximizes efficiency, reduces downtime, and provides a scalable framework for continuous workforce development.

Table 3 - XR Devices that will be supported by the XR5.0 Training Platform

#	XR Device
1	Microsoft HoloLens 2
2	Meta Quest 2/3/Pro
3	Magic Leap 2
4	Lenovo VFX
Future support - Apple Vision Pro, Pico, Sony and HTC Vive Focus 3	

4.4 Resources Scalability

Traditional IT infrastructures often suffer from underutilised hardware resources, requiring frequent costly upgrades to accommodate increasing performance demands. Enterprises must invest in new notebooks, workstations, or dedicated XR hardware to ensure smooth operation, leading to significant overhead costs and inefficiencies. The XR5.0 Training Platform eliminates these constraints by integrating with virtualisation platforms, ensuring that compute resources are dynamically allocated based on real-time demand.

Through virtualised resource management, the platform automatically provisions computing power the moment a user initiates an XR application. This on-demand resource allocation ensures that enterprises do not need to maintain excess computational capacity, thereby optimizing infrastructure utilisation while reducing capital expenditure. Instead of purchasing new hardware to meet increasing training demands, organizations can scale seamlessly without additional investments, allowing for cost-efficient expansion of their training programs. Furthermore, since no training data or applications are stored locally on user devices, trainees and operators can log in from any shared device using their credentials. This eliminates the need for dedicated hardware per user, maximizing device utilisation efficiency while ensuring

consistent access to training materials across different locations. This shared-resource model significantly enhances operational flexibility, allowing teams to deploy XR training at scale without concerns over device availability or compatibility.

By leveraging virtualisation and cloud-based streaming, the platform ensures that XR training remains highly scalable, cost-effective, and easily deployable. Enterprises can allocate resources dynamically, avoid unnecessary infrastructure upgrades, and provide seamless access to training applications from any device, maximizing efficiency while minimizing costs.

4.5 Maintain Security Standards

Data security is a critical aspect of any enterprise system, particularly in training environments where sensitive operational and user data, and user interactions must be protected. Traditionally, IT teams have had to manage security protocols on a device-by-device basis, increasing administrative overhead and introducing vulnerabilities when devices are lost, shared, or compromised. The XR5.0 Training Platform mitigates these risks through a fully centralised security model, ensuring that all data remains within the secure server infrastructure and never resides on end-user devices. The platform employs proprietary pixel streaming technology, called Hololight Stream, which enables real-time XR training experiences without transferring sensitive data to user devices. Hololight Stream ensures full control over sensitive data by preventing storage on XR devices, minimizing risks from device loss or cyberattacks, while its one-to-one server-client transmission reduces interception threats. Hololight Stream uses the WebRTC protocol wherein data is transmitted securely with Secure Real-time Transport Protocol (SRTP) and Session Controller Transport Protocol (SCTP) ensuring a robust and safe platform for data transmission.

This architecture eliminates risks associated with data breaches, local storage vulnerabilities, and unauthorised access. Since all processing and data handling occur on highly secured cloud servers, organizations can maintain strict control over training content, user interactions, and access permissions. Enterprise-grade encryption protocols protect all app and user data, both in transit and at rest, ensuring compliance with industry security standards.

Role-based Access Control (RBAC) further strengthens the security framework by allowing administrators to manage user permissions centrally. Each tenant, administrator, and user are granted access only to the necessary resources, preventing unauthorised data exposure. Single Sign-On (SSO) mechanisms enhance authentication security, ensuring that only verified users can access the training environment. Additionally, continuous monitoring and logging provide real-time insights into system activity, enabling proactive threat detection and compliance auditing. Automated security updates and patches are implemented across the cloud infrastructure, reducing vulnerabilities and ensuring that the platform remains resilient against evolving cyber threats.

By design, the platform prevents any data from being stored on local XR devices, ensuring that even in cases of device theft, loss, or compromise, no sensitive information is at risk. This cloud-first security approach not only simplifies IT management but also significantly enhances compliance with data protection regulations, making it an optimal solution for enterprise-scale XR training deployments.

4.6 Centralised User Analytics

The XR5.0 Training Platform incorporates a comprehensive analytics framework that provides administrators with real-time insights into application usage, user engagement, and training effectiveness. By centralising all analytics within a single platform, organisations can streamline management processes, optimise training content, and enhance decision-making without introducing additional complexity.

The usage analytics dashboard on the platform enables administrators to monitor key metrics, such as which applications are being used, the frequency and duration of usage, and user-specific interactions. This

granular level of detail allows organisations to assess the effectiveness of different training modules, identify patterns in user engagement, and determine which applications are most beneficial for workforce development. By tracking adoption rates and usage trends, enterprises can make data-driven decisions regarding app optimization, training adjustments, and future content development. Beyond basic usage tracking, location-based and session analytics provide insights into where and when training occurs. This is particularly valuable for distributed teams and enterprises operating in multiple locations, as it allows for region-specific performance assessments. The analytics engine also supports user performance tracking, enabling organisations to assess individual progress, identify skill gaps, and tailor training programs to meet specific workforce needs.

By centralizing analytics within the XR5.0 Training Platform, administrators benefit from a reduced management workload. Instead of manually gathering data from disparate sources, all information is readily available through an intuitive dashboard. This unified approach to monitoring and optimisation ensures that training applications remain effective, continuously improving based on real-world usage data. Furthermore, automated reporting tools allow for customised insights and periodic reviews, ensuring that enterprises remain agile in adapting their XR training strategies.

With data-driven insights, the platform empowers organisations to fine-tune their training ecosystem, enhance user experience, and ensure that XR5.0-enabled applications deliver measurable improvements in workforce skill development and operational efficiency.

4.7 Traditional Training Material Conversion to XR

Training content in traditional formats is rarely suitable for visualisation in immersive environments due to its static nature and lack of interactivity. To address this issue, the conversion of traditional materials is essential for a seamless transition to XR. The XR5.0 Training Platform enables the conversion of common file formats to XR versions. It provides tools to extract, enhance, and create content from traditional materials. Managers can extract content from PDFs to create checklists and workflows. Videos and images can be enhanced with annotations to provide related content. Future updates will introduce support for 3D models and LMS standards. Managers will be able to upload and integrate 3D models into training programs. This feature will create training experiences that traditional settings can't replicate. Also, the ability to import entire e-learning courses will enable a seamless integration of existing content in XR settings.

4.8 Immersive Training Material Visualisation

Visualizing training content in XR presents unique challenges. The dynamic nature of immersive environments demands responsive content adapted to user behaviour. Additionally, user interaction should be intuitive to ensure a seamless experience. The training platform tackles this issue providing immersive interfaces adapted to these requirements. All the interfaces support hand interaction and spatial anchoring. This allows for intuitive interactions and manipulation within the XR environment. Future updates will add support for scaling, gaze-based interactions, and a virtual dashboard. These features will enhance both user interactions and the display and organization of information within the virtual space.

4.9 Personalised and Adaptive XR Training Content

Content personalisation and adaptation to user profiles are essential for delivering tailored learning experiences. The training platform will address this by offering personalised and adaptive training content. Managers will be able to categorize training programs and materials to customize them to individual profiles. This ensures that specific programs and materials are accessible only to suitable users. In addition to static categorization, the content visualisation will dynamically adapt to each user. Based not only to the user profile but also on their behaviour, the interface will adjust in real-time to improve efficiency and usability.

5. PLATFORM DEPLOYMENT

5.1 Pilot Deployment

The following section describes and illustrates how the XR5.0 Training Platform will be leveraged by 6 pilots within the XR5.0 project to facilitate immersive, interactive and AI-enhanced industrial training experiences across various industrial domains. Below are the 6 pilots that focus on real-world use cases demonstrating the impact of the XR5.0 Training Platform in industrial training. Each of the pilots describe how they implement the platform in their use case supported by a high-level design architecture detailing the integration of the technical components used and the XR5.0 Training Platform. The technical progress and overall deployment and validation of the pilots will be captured within WP6.

At the time of writing this deliverable and given that the platform is planned for deployment closer to M20-M22, the following descriptions are provided at the pilot level, illustrating the platform's use within the pilot context.

Pilot 1 - Rapid Human Centric AI-Enabled Product Design (Pilot Leader - KUKA; Pilot Technical Responsible - ATB)

KUKA focuses on applying cutting-edge XR technologies and AI-driven solutions to enhance industrial processes, particularly in assembly lines and robotic commissioning. KUKA along with the pilot partners will leverage technologies such as XR, GenAI and HDT to optimize operations, improve training efficiency, and reduce human errors in real world industrial settings.

High Level Architecture:

Figure 37 - Pilot 1 High Level Architecture illustrating the use of the XR5.0 Training Platform

Description of workflow:

A manager from KUKA will:

- upload training materials such as LMS content (SCORM), 3D models, manuals (pdfs), Data sheets, training videos to the XR asset repository.
- upload the XR application developed by HOLO to the Hololight Hub.
- create training programs as step-by-step instructions dedicated to a specific maintenance procedure.
- manage users within the XR5.0 Training Platform with controlled access to specific XR training programs and XR apps based on their respective role and skill.
- review the user session and analyse data such as session time, training performance, feedback etc.

An on-site technician (commissioning, robot programmer, maintenance) will use the client application on the Microsoft HoloLens 2 XR device to launch the XR application assigned to the technician. The application will enable the operator to launch the training program and view files that the technician has access to. The application, running on the AWS cloud infrastructure and streamed to the Microsoft HoloLens 2 device, will communicate with the AI services (LLM engine and NSAI/AI) via APIs to visualise 3D models, recognize technical components and give generative assistance on installing and configuring them.

Pilot 2 - Human Centred Remote Maintenance and Asset Management (Pilot Leader - SH; Pilot Technical Responsible - OCU)

SH leverages XR technologies and AI-driven functionalities to enhance the remote maintenance of complex laboratory instruments. By enabling expert technicians to provide virtual support to less experienced field technicians, SH reduces the need for on-site maintenance, improving efficiency and minimizing downtime. Neurosymbolic AI models further enhance this process by assisting technicians in real-time problem-solving, ensuring faster and more effective issue resolution.

High Level Architecture:

Figure 38 - Pilot 2 High Level Architecture illustrating the use of the XR5.0 Training Platform

Description of workflow:

A manager configures user permissions, sets up custom workflows, and manages the knowledge base within OCU. The XR5.0 Training Platform is then linked to the OCU environment so users can import workflow steps into the training program, retrieve relevant documentation from the knowledge repository, and load a 3D model via Hologlight Stream. Whenever a trainee or on-site technician creates a service ticket, they can seamlessly open the matching XR training module during the ticket creation process, ensuring they have direct access to the guidance and resources they need. The data from that ticket is used to extend the knowledge base.

Pilot 3 - Operator 5.0 Training for Smart Water Pipes based on XR Streaming (Pilot Leader - EKSO; Pilot Technical Responsible - HOLO)

This pilot introduces an innovative approach to training maintenance technicians for smart water pipe systems using XR and AI technologies. By integrating AI-powered anomaly detection, it enhances technician training, reduces human error, accelerates fault identification, and improves overall efficiency. The Operator 5.0 Training for Smart Water Pipes pilot equips workers with the necessary skills to inspect and maintain advanced pipe systems safely, efficiently, and cost-effectively while addressing key challenges such as human errors, operator fatigue, and varying digital skills.

High Level Architecture:

Figure 39 - Pilot 3 High Level Architecture illustrating the use of the XR5.0 Training Platform

Description of workflow:

A manager from EKSO will:

- upload training materials such as pipe manuals (pdfs), training videos and vibration sensor data to the XR asset repository.
- upload the XR application developed by CYENS to the Hologlight Hub.
- create training programs as step-by-step instructions dedicated to a specific maintenance procedure.
- manage equipment/maintenance operators as users to the XR5.0 Training Platform with access control to specific XR training materials, training programs and XR apps based on role and skill.
- review the user session and analyse data such as session time, training performance etc.

An equipment/maintenance operator will use the client application on the Magic Leap 2 XR device to launch the XR application assigned to the operator. The application will enable the operator to launch the training program and view files that the operator has access to. The application, running on the AWS cloud infrastructure and streamed to the Magic Leap 2 device, will communicate with the AI services (LLM engine, NSAI/AL and Mage AI ETL) via APIs to visualise pipe sensors and anomaly data as well as chat with an AI bot that is trained on pipe maintenance operations.

Pilot 4 - Worker Centric Aircraft Maintenance Training (Pilot Leader - TAP; Pilot Technical Responsible - IML)

Within pilot 4, TAP enhances the training process for maintaining the Wing Anti-Ice Valve (WAIV), a critical aircraft component, using AI-enhanced XR environments. By integrating immersive virtual simulations, HDT, and real-time AI assistance, the project provides junior engineers at TAP with advanced training tools to optimize maintenance, improve accuracy, reduce errors, and prevent maloperation under high-stress conditions. This approach not only enhances efficiency but also ensures compliance with safety regulations.

High Level Architecture:

Figure 40 - Pilot 4 High Level Architecture illustrating the use of the XR5.0 Training Platform

Description of workflow:

The proposed architecture aims to develop an XR application to enhance aircraft maintenance technician training. At the core of this architecture is the Virtual Training (UC4.1) / Human Digital Twin (UC4.2) XR app. This application integrates several features to enhance virtual training such as interactive exploded views of 3D models, virtual procedure workflows and an immersive 3D environment.

The application also connects with various XR5.0 components to provide additional functionalities. It utilises the Training Platform for hosting and delivering the application, as well as for accessing training

content. The XR application is stored on the Hololight Hub and will be streamed using the Hololight Stream to a Hololight Stream Client, installed on the operator’s XR device. Also, it will connect to the Cloud Repository component to access training content. A manager can create training programs and materials using the XR5.0 Training Platform web interface. This content is stored in the cloud repository and accessed in the app for immersive visualisation.

The application will also integrate AI-powered features to enhance the virtual training environment. XR-enabled AL & NSAI models will aim to offer real-time image recognition and Generative AI Models to respond to user queries with information from training procedures.

In addition, HDTs will enable tracking the user’s behaviour to offer gesture and posture guidance in real time to improve training effectiveness. Other features include content personalisation and performance monitoring. Personalised XR content will adapt the training content based on user behaviour and profile. And physiological and performance monitoring ensures the training aligns with the user skills and improvement areas.

Pilot 5 - Increased Effectiveness and Safety of Product Assembly and Repair Processes (Pilot Leader - SPACE; Pilot Technical Responsible - SYN)

In pilot 5, SPACE enhances the efficiency and safety of assembling and repairing edge devices using AI-enhanced XR technologies. By providing personalised training modules and real-time remote support, the pilot empowers SPACE’s technicians with tailored instructions for assembly, maintenance, and repair. Designed for all skill levels, from beginners to intermediate technicians, this approach ensures safer, more efficient workflows and improved overall performance.

High Level Architecture:

Figure 41 - Pilot 5 High Level Architecture illustrating the use of the XR5.0 Training Platform

Description of workflow:

The pilot aims to improve the training of technicians involved in the assembly, installation, and maintenance of certain IOT solutions offered by the pilot leader. The training is delivered via a pilot-specific XR Application and is streamed to the XR devices utilizing Hololight Stream.

During the training creation phase, managers and expert engineers create training programs (utilizing the Training Programs Authoring Tool). Those programs are then stored in the Cloud Repository. At this stage, the creation phase is manual, but in the subsequent phases, we foresee utilizing the Generative AI models produced by XR5.0 to automate at least part of it.

During the training phase, the technicians connect to the Hololight Hub and stream the appropriate training modules (using Hololight Stream). The module selection is based on the HDT’s assessment of their skill level/needs. Lastly via the use of a smartwatch and motion/eye tracking from the XR Device, information about the engagement and performance of the trainee is fed back to the HDT so that metrics like trainee engagement or performance can be evaluated.

Pilot 6 - Human Centric Guidance and Troubleshooting for Customer Service (Pilot Leader - LNS; Pilot Technical Responsible - SSF)

In Pilot 6, LNS enhances maintenance and troubleshooting for complex machines using AI-enhanced XR technologies. By providing personalised, real-time support tailored to individual skill levels, the pilot optimizes troubleshooting and planned maintenance processes. This approach improves efficiency, reduces downtime, and enhances technician satisfaction.

High level Architecture:

Figure 42 - Pilot 6 High Level Architecture illustrating the use of the XR5.0 Training Platform.

Description of workflow:

The manager assigns tasks to technicians via the web interface. Technicians can access detailed maintenance information using XR devices such as Almer, RealWear, or tablets. The maintenance steps are

customized based on the technician's skill set. If additional support is needed, the troubleshooting video call feature enables technicians to contact an expert for real-time guidance. Through the video stream, the expert can see and hear the technician, assisting in resolving the issue effectively. All interventions are documented and stored for analysis and workflow optimization.

5.2 Beyond XR5.0

The previous section details the method in which each XR5.0 pilot will leverage the XR5.0 Training Platform to satisfy the industrial training needs and requirements demonstrated through specific user stories and use case scenarios. Within XR5.0 project, the XR5.0 Training Platform is transforming industrial training by providing cloud-based scalable and secure immersive, interactive, and intelligent training environments across multiple sectors such as product design and commissioning, remote maintenance and asset management, water pipe network rehabilitation and maintenance, aircraft maintenance and training, product assembly and repair processes and, industrial maintenance and troubleshooting for customer service.

By leveraging advanced AI models, HDTs, and cloud-based XR services, the platform bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, ensuring a more competent and prepared workforce.

While the XR5.0 Training Platform is designed primarily for industrial training, its architecture, services, and AI-powered features enable applications beyond the six primary pilot use cases discussed in the previous section. The platform's customizability, adaptability and scalability, as well as device-agnostic approach, allows it to be leveraged in diverse fields, from education and research to remote collaboration, public safety, defence and soft skills development. Below are additional domains where the XR5.0 Training Platform can have significant impact:

- Remote Collaboration and 3D Virtual Workspaces
 - Use Cases - Virtual office space.
- Industries - Automotive, Aerospace, Construction, Defence, Marine
 - Use Cases - Training; 3D visualisation; Situational Awareness
- Higher Education and Research
 - Use Cases - Medical Training
- Smart City Planning and Infrastructure Development
 - Use Cases - XR powered simulation.
- Public Safety and Emergency Response Training
 - Use Cases - Situational Awareness; Fire simulation; Training

The XR5.0 Training Platform extends far beyond traditional industrial applications, demonstrating its versatility across multiple domains. From education and research to public safety, smart city planning, and remote collaboration, the platform enables immersive, scalable, and data-driven training experiences. By integrating AI-powered analytics, cloud-based XR environments, and digital twin technology, the platform redefines how knowledge is acquired, shared, and applied across industries.

6. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

This deliverable has outlined the technical architecture, key features, and implementation strategy for the XR5.0 Training Platform, which aims to provide immersive, AI-driven, and human-centric XR training solutions for industrial operators. By detailing the system components, integration mechanisms, and real-world applications, the report establishes the foundational framework upon which the platform will be built. The centralised app and user management system, security-first architecture, AI-enhanced analytics, and scalable infrastructure ensure that the platform is robust, adaptable, and aligned with Industry 5.0 principles.

At this stage, the first version of the XR5.0 Training Platform is focused on defining and integrating its core components while aligning with the technical and operational requirements of industrial partners. The initial pilot applications will provide valuable insights into usability, performance, and deployment challenges, which will be crucial for refining the system further. The development efforts so far have laid a solid groundwork for the full implementation of the XR5.0 Training Platform, but several aspects still require enhancements and iterative improvements.

The next version of this deliverable, D5.4 - Training Platform for Operator 5.0 v2 planned for M27, will provide an in-depth evaluation of the pilot implementations, assess the impact and effectiveness of the platform, and incorporate improvements based on industry feedback. It will further validate the scalability and real-world application of the training platform, ensuring it fully meets the long-term objectives of the XR5.0 project. Furthermore, it will provide an updated assessment of the platform's development, focusing on optimization, validation, and potential extensions to further enhance its usability and effectiveness.

By continuously iterating and improving upon this foundation, the XR5.0 Training Platform aims to redefine workforce training in industrial environments, leveraging XR and AI technologies to enhance skill development, operational efficiency, and long-term adaptability.

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